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- ✓ IJTIMOIIY FANLAR

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THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON INTERNATIONAL TOURIST ARRIVALS TO UZBEKISTAN, GRAVITY APPLIED APPROACH

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Abstract. *Tourism industry is highly sensitive to climate change and can significantly affect tourist's behaviour and destination choice. This study analyzes the impact of climate change on bilateral tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan from 67 countries using traditional gravity models for the period 2013-2018. As a result, higher average temperature reduces slightly the number of international tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan. High precipitation in the origin countries could generate more tourists in the nature of Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *tourism, climate change, holiday temperature, destination choice, ecotourism*

ВЛИЯНИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ КЛИМАТА НА ПРИБЫТИЕ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ТУРИСТОВ В УЗБЕКИСТАН, ГРАВИТАЦИОННЫЙ ПОДХОД

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Аннотация. *Индустрия туризма очень чувствительна к изменению климата и может существенно повлиять на поведение туристов и выбор направлений. В данном исследовании анализируется влияние изменения климата на двусторонние туристические прибытия в Узбекистан из 67 стран с использованием традиционных гравитационных моделей за период 2013-2018 годов. В результате повышение средней температуры несколько снижает количество международных туристических прибытий в Узбекистан. Высокие осадки в странах происхождения могут привлечь больше туристов на природу Узбекистана.*

Ключевые слова: *туризм, изменение климата, температура отдыха, выбор направления, экотуризм*

Introduction & literature review. Tourism plays a magnificent role in the economic growth of Uzbekistan. The total contribution of travel and tourism was estimated 4.5% of total economy (Total T&T GDP = UZS21,831.1BN), total visitor exports is UZS13,688.5BN (21.1% of total exports) and 601 thousand jobs (4.6% of total employment) related to tourism sector [12, p.1]. Specifically, the number of international tourists arrivals reached to 1, 4 billion and 5% growth of tourism exports in 2018 [13, p.2]. International tourist arrivals in Uzbekistan have recorded a dramatic rise by 98% and reached 6,4 million in 2018 [9, p.3]. Uzbekistan attracts tourists with its rich history, diverse culture and traditions, beautiful nature and continental climate. There is a wide range of opportunities for the rapid development of ecological, cultural, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, health, rural, industrial and business tourism in Uzbekistan. The potential of tourism in Uzbekistan has been estimated as 7.4 thousands cultural and natural heritage cities. Ancient cities, such as Khiva, Bukhara, Samarkand and Shakhrisabz have been included in the UNESCO's "World Heritage lists" [3, p.73], ecotourism as a new type of tourism is likely to improve because of rich natural resources, including more than 60 reserves and national parks (Zarafshan, Ugam-Chotkol, Nurata, Zaamin and others), 60 forestries and more than 400 unique natural monuments (Hayitboyev et al., 2010) [4, p.38]. For example, Zaamin national park has a typical mountain climate with spruce forests, beautiful landscape, fresh air and full of greenery. Winter tourism can be improved since winter in the park lasts 5 months. Uzbekistan has also a great opportunity to improve speleo tourism which has more than 500 caves.

Uzbekistan is a landlocked country in the middle of Central Asia which causes low rainfall, hot and severe drought. The continental climate is characterized by: open and sunny skies; the temperature is too high, the annual precipitation is low, and the possible (potential) evaporation is high; summers are long and hot, and winters are somewhat cold for this latitude; the difference in annual and daily temperatures is large. These features of the Uzbek climate depend, first of all, on the factors that create the climate. Summers in Uzbekistan are dry and hot, with the average temperature $+26 + 30^{\circ} \text{C}$ which is over average holiday temperature 15.49 C [5, p.16] and highly expected to deter international tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan.

Climate change is one of the important factors in the destination choice. For this reason a number of researchers (e.g. Hamilton et al. [5, p.3]; Bigano et al. 2006 [2, p.90]; Bhatt et al.[8, p.3]; Berritella et al. [1, p.5]; Layne et al. [7, p4]; and others) have focused on the impact of climate change on tourism. The rise of

temperatures will eventually reduce winter sports destinations viabilities, affect biodiversity and eventually ecotourism and lead to more forest fires (the destination impacts); decreasing water availability could lead to disputes with local industry and communities (the operational impacts) Bigano et al. [2, p.395] revealed that the Dutch and German tourists prefer to travel in moderate temperature rather than tourists from the Netherlands. Moreover, the influence of climate change on global tourism has been investigated by Hamilton et al. [5, p.18]. A simulation model that includes international tourism flows between 207 countries for the years of 1980, 1985, 1990, 1995. Climate change's effect on international tourism is argued using the extended form of HTM (Hamburg Tourism Model). Specifically, A1B model scenario is used, including population growth estimates, economic development and expected departure and arrival of international tourism during the period 2000-2070. The result showed that travellers from temperate climates are more likely to choose home countries rather than foreign ones. Indeed, climate change impacts global tourism, but not as much as population growth and per capita income. By compromising estimation of CO2 emission for different flows of prospective international tourism, Hamilton et al. improved their former research. The importance of climate change on destination choice was examined by Rosselló et al. [6, p.10] for the year of 1995-2010. A demand model for global tourism was estimated, including the main classic determinants that, allowing a time-varying climatic sensitivity of tourists. Bilateral tourism flows between 178 countries has been estimated by using a gravity model for international travels over fifteen years. It has been found that, how turning point temperatures of origin and destination countries have changed over the fifteen years and traditional warm destinations competitiveness has been lost. Moreover, project and plot future international tourism flows, GDP per capita income, demographic change as well as precipitation for 2080 within three A2,B1,B2 climate change simulations. The effect of temperature on projected tourist arrivals for 2080 based on A1, B1, B2 scenarios has been represented evidently, On the other hand analysis percentage change in tourist arrivals (change in temperature and GDP per capita was taken into account) was based on A2,B1,B2 scenarios. Walsh et al. [11, p.3] extended on previous research work by Bigano et al. [2, p.390] and assessed the impact of climate on the choice of tourist destination for 182 countries from 1995 to 2009 and destination choice model was used for all countries. The destination choice is connected by the tourist arrivals' socio-economic characteristics from the country of origin and also climate variables. Political stability is statically important, with a detrimental

effect, which implies a lack of referentiality for tourists from politically stable countries to stable destinations. As a result, The Mediterranean region has found a very attractive holiday destination in relation to its current climate. Especially, $15.49\text{ C} \pm 0.20$ as the average optimal holiday temperature was found to be insensitive to the country of origin of the travellers from Russia and Canada prefer the same temperature at their destination of choice.

As climate change is considered as an important factor in tourism flows, especially for types of tourism related to nature: ecotourism, nature tourism, sky tourism, sport tourism and others. The research aims to analyse how climate change (including temperature) impacts on international tourism flows in Uzbekistan. Abovementioned researchers and specialists have analyzed these factors for foreign countries; however climate, temperature influences on tourism arrivals in Uzbekistan have not been conducted yet.

Methodology and data. The methodology used in this research to estimate the influence of climate change on global tourism arrivals is gravity model. This model has been commonly used in empiric research as a consequence of its fitness. Because, it is forecasted that global tourism arrivals will increase along with economic size. One of the well recognized works of Jan Tinbergen [10, p.20] is the scale of bilateral trade transactions between any two countries, using the "gravity equation" as equivalent to Newton's universal law of gravitation, defines patterns of foreign exchange. The formula assumes that the trade flows between the two countries are directly proportional to the economic volumes of the countries and inversely proportional to the difference between them. Gravity models are commonly used to describe international movements such as commerce, migration, foreign direct investment and, more recently, tourism. The equation (2) is a simplified variant of the gravity equation, which represents the amount of global tourist arrivals from countries of origin and destination at the time of arrival.

$$\ln Q_{ijt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln \text{DISTANCE}_{ij} + \beta_2 \ln \text{GDPpc}_{it} + \beta_2 \ln \text{GDPpc}_{jt} + \varepsilon_{ijt} \quad (2)$$

The following final baseline model (Eq.3.) which estimates the effect of climate change and other variables on international tourism flows has been established following a study of the literature and the methodological techniques and econometric results of the projected model.

$$\ln Q_{ijt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln \text{GDPpc}_{it} + \beta_2 \ln \text{GDPpc}_{jt} + \beta_3 \ln \text{POPULATION}_{it} + \beta_4 \ln \text{POPULATION}_{jt} + \beta_5 \ln \text{DISTANCE}_{ij} + \beta_{11} \text{TEMP}_i + \beta_{12} \text{TEMP}_j + \beta_{15} \text{PREC}_i + \beta_{16} \text{PREC}_j + \mu_{ijt} \quad (3)$$

Where;

- Ln defines natural logarithms;
- i and j are sub – index denotes to the country of origin and destination, t is a six year time period (2013-2018);
- μ_{ijt} is a well-behaved disturbance term;

Climate variables remain stable in the final reference model, as they address the effects of the predicted environment on global tourism flows rather than the real influence of climate change, in other words, it is interested that tourism 's climate assumptions such that climate change stays consistent over time rather than evolving over time. The function, presumed in this research, was estimated using Random effect model.

On the other hand, the reason for the rejection of the Fixed Effect model is that the Fixed Effects model cannot be used to evaluate time-invariant variables. For this reason Random Effects model is used to analyze the influence of climate change on global tourist flows from 67 countries of origin to Uzbekistan for the period of 2008-2018.

Data Specification

- $lnDISTANCE_{ij}$ Measures the distance between capital cities from the countries of origin to the destination in wide circles;
- $lnGDPpc_{it}$ and $lnGDPpc_{jt}$ defines respectively, GDP per capita of origin countries and the destination at time t ;
- $lnPOPULATION_{it}$ and $lnPOPULATION_{jt}$ are the density of population of origin countries and the destination at time t ;
- $TEMP_i$ and $TEMP_j$ are the annual average temperature of the countries of origin and destination, as well as $TEMP_i^2$ and $TEMP_j^2$ are the square average annual temperature of origin and destination countries in degree Celsius;
- $PREC_i$ and $PREC_j$ are the total average precipitation of the countries of origin and destination, as well as $PRECi^2$ and $PRECj^2$ are the annual average annual precipitation of the countries of origin and the destination in millimeters;
- WET_i and WET_j Such indicators reflect the wet-day duration of origin and destination countries, calculated by days;
- CLD_j and CLD_i are the cloud cover percentage of origin countries and the destination;

- WND_j and WND_i are the observation of wind speed of origin countries and the destination, measured by meters per second
- SSH_j and SSH_i are sunshine duration in hours/day of origin countries and the destination;
- VAP_i and VAP_i Z shows the steam pressure dimension of the countries of origin and destination, the measures by hectare-Pascals.

Results

Table 1.1 Descriptive statistics, illustrates descriptive statistics of used variables in this study.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
tou	504	71652.37	299104.5	1	3100000
gdppc_dest	506	1936.855	509.4516	1082.286	2615.025
gdppc_dest	506	1936.855	509.4516	1082.286	2615.025
pop_dest	506	3.02e+07	1773673	2.73e+07	3.30e+07
pop_orig	506	9.59e+07	2.68e+08	343452	1.39e+09
distance	506	3803.66	2116.762	340.001	11454.6
wet_day	506	5.283333	0	5.283333	5.283333
temp_orig	484	12.18712	7.933739	.6833333	27.625
temp_dest	506	12.075	0	12.075	12.075
prec_dest	506	29.50625	0	29.50625	29.50625
prec_orig	495	120.9257	83.51638	8.98125	410.3062
cloudcover	506	42.43333	0	42.43333	42.43333
vapour	506	7.6	0	7.6	7.6
wind	506	5.55	0	5.55	5.55
sunshine	506	38.89167	0	38.89167	38.89167

Table 1.2 The impact of climate change on the tourism demand of Uzbekistan (RE)

Random-effects GLS regression	Number of obs	=	482
Group variable: idorig	Number of groups	=	44
R-sq:	Obs per group:		
within = 0.0359	min =		10
between = 0.512	avg =		11.0
overall = 0.4571	max =		11
	Wald chi2(6)	=	80.53
corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)	Prob > chi2	=	0.0000

(Std. Err. adjusted for 44 clusters in idorig)

	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
lnpoporig	.9686599	.1780333	5.44	0.000	.6197209	1.317599
lnpopdest	4.588406	1.450124	3.16	0.002	1.746215	7.430597
lngdpdest	-1.096363	.3223842	-3.40	0.001	-1.728224	-.4645015
lndist	-2.803333	.4391879	-6.38	0.000	-3.664125	-1.94254
temp_orig	-.0389632	.0358334	-1.09	0.000	-.1091953	.0312689
prec_orig	.0039529	.0033774	1.17	0.002	-.0026667	.0105725
_cons	-57.41424	24.62878	-2.33	0.020	-105.6858	-9.142726
sigma_u	2.0176933					
sigma_e	1.4205336					
rho	.66859664	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

Table 1.2 shows how climate variable explain international tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan for 2008-2018 using gravity model. The annual panel data is

strongly balanced. The result shows a medium goodness of fit, the dependent variable is explained 45% by series of explanatory variables. Gross domestic product per capita (Ingdpdest) is statistically significant and has a negative impact on international tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan, suggesting that a slump in economic output in Uzbekistan leads to a reduction of personal income. This is, highly fall international tourists arrivals to Uzbekistan by 1%. Transport cost (Indist) is statistically significant and has a negative effect on tourism demand of Uzbekistan. How far between Uzbekistan and tourist sending countries, it increases travel cost and time which intensely decrease the number of international tourists by 2%. Tourists from far origin countries would prefer to travel nearby destination rather than Uzbekistan. The number of populations is a proxy of human capital of origin (Inpoporig) and destination (Uzbekistan) countries are statistically significant at 5% level and have positive influence on tourist arrivals, implying that the more number of population the higher number of tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan. The effect of climate change is so small, especially average temperature and rainfall in origin countries are statistically significant at 5% level. The rest of climate variables such wind speed, number of sunshine days, cloud cover, vapour, wetday in the origin and Uzbekistan are omitted from the estimated model. Average temperature (temp_orig) in the origin countries negatively related to the number of international tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan indicating that the higher temperature in the origin countries tends tourists to stay their host countries rather than traveling to Uzbekistan. However, higher frequency of rainfall in the origin (prec_orig) countries motivate tourists to travel Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

In the last decade, the number of travelers visiting Uzbekistan has increased dramatically. Because of the improvement of tourism infrastructure, quality of services and advertisement. However, some factors should be taken into account which deters increasing this number eventually, such as high cost of transportation, high temperature and precipitation. This study shows the impact of climate change on international tourist arrivals in Uzbekistan for the period 2008-2018 using the gravity model. Gravity determinants are highly approved theory and well explained in the estimated model. The results reveal that tourism demand of Uzbekistan is not highly dependent on climate issues however average temperature and precipitation have significant effects. The fluctuation of average temperature and precipitation in the origin countries could change slightly the tourism demand of Uzbekistan but the potential influences rate so small.

Interestingly, travel cost is a factor which tends to reduce international tourists in Uzbekistan by 2%. Hence, policy makers should moderate transport cost depending on the destination of tourists coming from during peak tourism season.

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